

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE EPIC “GARIB-ASHIQ” IT’S PERFORMANCE BY KARAKALPAK BAKHSHIS, AND ITS SCIENTIFIC STUDY

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Abstract

We explored the history of the Karakalpak folk epic “GARIB-ASHIQ” and how it was orally transmitted from generation to generation by bakhshis during captivity, using as an example the genealogy of the bakhshis who performed this epic.

Keywords: epic, genesis, plot, motif, folklore, variant, version, image, bakhshi.

Introduction

The Karakalpak people possess not only numerous heroic epics but also a rich tradition of love epics. These love epics have emerged and developed among the Karakalpaks, as well as other related and Turkic peoples, since ancient times and continues to be performed to this day. Among these epics, «Gharip Ashiq», «Sayatkhon-Hamire», and «Ashiq-Najep» can be specifically highlighted as having spread widely among the people and become part of the bakhshis' (traditional bards) regular repertoire.

One of the scholars who has extensively studied these Karakalpak love epics, A. Alymov, points out the following. For example, «The Arzu» school is distinguished by its development of performing arts in the Aral region dialect. Despite this school emerging in the 19th century, it is considered a developed creative continuation of the schools of great jiravs and bakhshis such as Jiyeu, Khalmurat, Shankot, Jiyemurat, Eshbay, Niyazymbet, Akymbet, and others who lived and created in the 16th-17th centuries [1]. The formation period of Karakalpak bakhshis was closely connected with their migration to Khorezm. According to historical sources of the Karakalpaks, for example, «The Karakalpaks living in the Nogai Khanate along the Volga were forced to migrate to the banks of the Syr Darya in the second half of the 16th century after the Khanate disintegrated under pressure from the Russian Tsardom. After arriving along the Amu Darya River in the 17th century, they maintained close ties with the Khiva Khanate» [2]. Based on this information, we can say without error that the formative period of Karakalpak bakhshi's art occurred primarily after their migration to Khorezm.

According to the renowned scholar N. Davqaraev: «This type of dastan spread among the Karakalpak people after the 17th century, especially during the 19th century, through the Turkmens and Khorezmian Uzbeks, or in manuscript form. Among the Karakalpaks, they learned from the famous Turkmen “*baxshi*” Suyev, who lived for a long time in the 19th century, and from the Khorezmian Uzbek “*baxshi*” Eshbay, and perform in their style», [3] he notes.

Davqaraev suggests that dastans likely originated after the 17th century. In our opinion, if the dastans were formed in the same century as the «Garib-ashiq» dastan in the 16th century, then the performers of the

dastan must have formed during that period. This is because both the creators and performers of the epic poem were *jirovs* and *baxshis*. Much information is provided about *jirovs* in the 14th-16th-17th centuries. This suggests that the art of *jirov* developed during these centuries, and the art of *baxshi* may have been secondary. Our classical poets Kunxoja and Ajiniyoz, Berdaq, who lived in the 19th century, also practiced *baxshi*. Therefore, it is clear that Kunxoja and Ajiniyoz, Berdaq also learned the art of *baxshi* from anyone, and they too had mentors. Thus, the art of bakhshi among the Karakalpaks was formed before the 19th century; on the contrary, in the 19th century, the art of bakhshi became widespread among the Karakalpak people and reached a stage of development. To confirm this point, let's turn to the work of Q. Maqsetov. For example: “Berdaq's friends, Aqimbet the bard, Arzi the bard from Orol, and the Turkmen bard Suyev and Otesh, frequently visited his home. Moreover, they have celebrated weddings together several times. These events were recorded by Q. Maqsetov in 1957 from old Perne, the wife of Hurliman's eldest son, Ablatdin [4]. According to this information, this indicates a significant development of the art of *baxshi* among the Karakalpaks in the 19th century.

Q. Ayimbetov supports these views, stating: «The works and repertoires of Karakalpak folk singers, namely bakhshis, storytellers, and poets, encompassing the 18th-19th centuries, demonstrate their connection to the Khorezm period and emphasize the widespread development of Karakalpak bakhshi art». [5]. The epics «Garib-ashiq», «Yusuf-Ahmad», and «Sayatxon-Hamira», performed by bakhshis in the 18th-19th centuries, along with the «Gorogli» epic, are part of the permanent repertoire of Karakalpak bakhshis. These epics were performed by our classical poets Kunxoja, Ajiniyoz, and Berdaq. The names of the heroes of this epic, the events, the era and geographical environment, the names of cities, places, and waters remain unchanged, and even if so, they are not significant. It has been preserved in all variants to this day. The inclusion of the *Garib-oshiq* epic in the repertoire of Karakalpak *baxshi* (folk singers) demonstrates the strong influence of the Khorezm and Turkmen *baxshi* (folk singers). The *Garib-oshiq* (The Stranger-Lover) epic's inclusion in the repertoire of Karakalpak *baxshi* (folk singers)

demonstrates the strong influence of the Khorezm and Turkmen *baxshi* (folk singers).

Firstly, because they lived in the same region as these peoples, and secondly, because Karakalpak bakhshis became their students, they took them as their mentors and learned their performing skills. These master-disciple traditions became a tradition among the bakhshis of these three countries, and the friendly relations between them strengthened day by day. This opinion can be demonstrated through the scholarly work of N. Davqaraev. For example, «Every school bakhshi had their own vocal technique and repertoire. 1. The beloved Turkmen bakhshi, along with his disciples: Japaq, Bala bakhshi, Janaboy, and others, has a strong Khorezm tradition in their performance technique and performs in the Khorezm (Aral) dialect of the Uzbek language. There are also many changes in the melodies». Musa Baxshi's students include: Esjon, Juman, Qarajon, Patilla, Aymurza, Kalbala, Sapar, Tiniboy, and others. They sang in pure Karakalpak, Karakalpak songs to Karakalpak melodies, and love epics translated into Karakalpak, such as «G'arib ashiiq», «Yusuf-Ahmad», and «Sayatxon-Hamira», [5]. Regarding the origins of Karakalpak bakhshi art, Q. Ayimbetov states: «The bakhshis of the Aral Sea Uzbeks exchanged repertoires with Turkmen and Karakalpak bakhshis, interacting with each other. Uzbek and Karakalpak bakhshis share many melodies performed by bakhshis. The renowned Turkmen bakhshi Suyev trained many students from the island Uzbeks. Among them, Adilboy and his students O'rinboy, Janaboy, and Tora were bakhshis. It is noted that the famous bards of the Aral Uzbeks were Qutim, Alliyar, Gurbek, Adilbay, Janabay, Orinbay» [6].

As we mentioned above, Suyuv mentions that even before the bakhshis, there were also bakhshis, namely Atash, Garibniyoz, Nurjon, and Otesh. As we can see, the Karakalpak bakhshi art, thanks to such friendly relations with the bakhshis of Turkmenistan, Khorezm, and the Aral Sea region of Uzbekistan, exchanged master and student performances with each other, learning the secrets of music and melody from each other, gaining experience, processing and developing it, expanding their repertoire. Such friendly collaborations were especially strong. Musa the bard and Suyuv the bard maintained close ties. They exchanged melodies from each other's repertoires and taught them. Therefore, it is correct that N. Davqarayev indicates that Musa baxshi's students perform in the pure Karakalpak language. This is because he became a student of Musa Baxshi and, following in his footsteps, also adapted the aforementioned epics and melodies, performing them in pure Karakalpak.

N. Davqarayev, the founder of Karakalpak folklore, Q. Ayimbetov, and Candidate of Art Sciences T. Adambaeva, who extensively researched the great contributions of Karakalpak performers, indicate: «According to their performance characteristics, they are divided into four schools: the Aqimbet-Musa school, the Suyuv school, the Arzi school, and the Orinboy school. Of course, these are conditionally divided, and as such, distinctive features are also found among them». In the repertoires of all these schools, love epics such as «Garib ashiiq», «Yusuf-Ahmad», and

«Sayatxon-Hamira» hold a prominent place. Because each such school had its own performance skills, the technique of performing melodies, and their own specific direction. Thus, for centuries, storytellers, one after another, became teachers and students, received blessings from their teachers, and thoroughly studied and performed the teachers' melodies and epics, passing them on to future generations. The majority of storytellers were primarily gifted with the ability to compose poems, possessing impressionability when their spirits were lifted and they could even recite them fluently from memory. This tradition of storytelling was fully formed and developed among the Karakalpak people, giving them their own melodies, songs, and epics. They acquired their own solo performance repertoire, skills, and techniques. They refined and enriched them, teaching them to their students and passing them down from generation to generation.

As mentioned above, Aqimbet baxshi was one of the first to develop the Karakalpak art of bakhshi and train his followers, namely disciples. His students were Musa, Edenbay, Bayniyoz, Xoja bola, and Dosnazar baxshi. Among them, the renowned and well-known figures, Musa baxshi and Edenbay, became the most skilled performers. These two *baxshi* elevated the Karakalpak art of *baxshi* to new heights, expanding the repertoire of the art of *baxshi* and performing them in two groups: the *nama`*s of Musa Baxshi and the *nama`*s of Edenbay Baxshi. Musa Baxshi's followers trained Esjon, Juman, Qarajon, Patilla, Aymurza, Kalbala, Sapar, Tiniboy, and others. Alongside these bakhshis, Berdaq's daughter, Hurliman bakhshi, also flourished. Hurliman learned the secrets of bakhshi from her father, Berdaq. They were skilled performers of Karakalpak melodies and songs.

In the 19th century, the art of bakhshi performed by the Karakalpak people developed very rapidly. During this period, Berdaq maintained close contact with the contemporaries of the poets Aqimbet and Musa, teaching them many things and learning much from them. Berdaq greatly influenced them with his poetry and *baxshi*. As an example, we can cite Berdaq's poems dedicated to Aqimbet the bard and Musa the bard. For example, in his poem «Musa the Bard», Berdaq describes Musa as «the sultan of bards», «the king who amazed him», «the soul melted with music», and «the summer of the heart that blossomed.» [6]. In the continuation of this song, the poets Berdaq, Edenbay, Xolmurod, Bayniyoz, Oten, Alloniyoz, Jumaniyoz, Qurbon, Shalabay, Qutlimurod, Seytnazar, Durisbergen, and Begniyoz are mentioned. As we can see, the 19th century marked a period of flourishing of the art of *baxshi* performance among the Karakalpaks.

Methods

In the 20th century, following in the footsteps of these great masters, they enriched their repertoires, gained the attention of the people, and served flawlessly. Among the bakhshis were Karajan bakhshi, Aytjan bakhshi, Bayniyaz bakhshi, Japaq bakhshi, Esjan bakhshi, Kyz bakhshi Kanigul, Amet bakhshi Tariykhov, Tileumurat bakhshi, Genjebay Tileumuratov, Turganbay Kurbanov. These were very skilled, talented, and eloquent bards of the 20th century. It was the bakhshis who saw the school of the aforementioned great

masters, received their upbringing, learned from them, mastered all their skills and melodies, developed them, enriched their repertoire, and passed it on to the next generation through the path of master-student.

The epic poem "Garib Ashiq" will undoubtedly be included in the repertoire of Karakalpak folk bards. Because in the epic poem "Garib ashik," the image of Shohsanam, the highest form of human emotion - love - is fully depicted. She does not acknowledge the boundaries of any social strata and stands above the concept of being truly rich in love and poor. Shaxsanam, in her love for Garib, opposes both her father and mother. She sees her happy future in Garib's love. Compared to his love for G'arib, wealth, palaces, gardens, and fortresses are worth nothing. Shaxsanam is portrayed as a figure who fought for her love, devoted to it with all her heart and soul, and deeply cherished it. His/Her reason, purpose, is to be faithful to his/her love, to achieve it. His acting according to his conscience, refusing to face his mother's resistance, his father's tyranny, or Shawlath's trap, serves as clear evidence of this. The beauty and special significance of Shaxsanam's image are primarily valued for its alignment with the external appearance of her inner world. Her beauty and intelligence embody the image of women, elevated to a typical level in folklore. In it, we can see the best qualities of girls, characteristic of the poetry of Turkic peoples.

The epic poem "Garib ashik" (The Stranger in Love) clearly demonstrates the skillful use of rich forms of folk songs. These songs are widely popular among the people due to their inclusion in the dastan. For example: "Mother, don't torment me anymore," "You've separated me," "My dear mullah, for a while free this beloved," "If you want to, take Sanam to your dwelling," "My son, I entrust you to God," "Dear brother, where are you going," "They'll kill me if I go, I'll die if I don't go," "From your pain," "Will my flower not bloom," "The beloved's flower has come, it hasn't come by itself," "It will come swaying, swaying," "Wonderful," "My stranger," "I am a Dagly, a Dagly," "My dear Sanam," "Welcome, my stranger, you've come with joy," "My darling," "Sanam's," "I fell for the love of a beloved and came," "I couldn't find comfort since my beloved left," "Give my beloved safe," "If honor and pride [6]. These songs raised the fame of the epic poem "Garib ashik" to great heights. The love of the poor lover and Shaxsanam became legendary, celebrated by the entire nation. It wouldn't be an exaggeration to say that there isn't a bakhshi among the Karakalpaks who hasn't performed or sung the epic poem "Garib Ashiq". Therefore, the epic poem "Garib Ashiq" has earned a full place in the repertoire of Karakalpak folk bards. These songs are considered among the most beautiful of all Karakalpak folk poetry.

Of course, such songs won't just be performed by themselves; they need a good, melodious bakhshi (folk singer) to give them rhythm, a suitable melody, and suitable musical instruments. These occupy a special place. According to N. Davqarayev: "Musical instruments are called *qobiz*, *dombra*, *duwtar*, *nay*, *balaman*, *sibizgi*, *chin qobiz*, and *sirnays*. There are many types of songs sung by bakhshis. Therefore, their melodies are diverse. The storytellers sing to many melodies. The

practice of fortune-telling among the Karakalpaks flourished after they migrated to Central Asia and Khorezm. Therefore, the influence of Eastern peoples is strong in the repertoires and melodies of bakhshis [3].

Certainly, the role of neighboring Khorezm and Turkmen bards plays a special role in the formation and development of Karakalpak national melodies. By thoroughly studying these melodies, he developed individual Karakalpak melodies. Karakalpak bakhshis primarily performed with the *dutor*, *nay*, and *balaman*, while some performers also performed with the *dutor* itself. Lately, the *girjak* has been playing alongside the *dutor*.

It can be argued that the entire nation sang the epic poem "Garib ashik" (The Stranger in Love) alongside the bards. The contributions of Aqimbet and Musa Baxshi, who played a significant role in shaping the Karakalpak version of the "Garib Ashiq", both in terms of words and melody, are immense. All Karakalpak masters of the word, up to their students Eschan bakhshi and Japaq bakhshi, loved to recite the dastan "Garib ashik" and made a special contribution to the formation of their own versions.

Of course, it's not the author of the epic that drives the interest in epic poetry. The Karakalpak bakhshi poets Aqimbet, Musa, Suyuv, Juman, Abboz, Mavlik, Orinboy, Jopoq, Eshon, Amet, and many others, influenced the development and gradual flourishing of any of the epic poems of Eastern poets. The influence of the cultural ties of the fraternal peoples played a crucial role in the formation and development of Karakalpak folk love epics. In the folklore section of his extensive research on the history of Karakalpak literature, N. Davqaraev offers valuable insights into the epics that spread among the Karakalpaks under the influence of related peoples. He noted that, starting from the 17th century, connections with the indigenous peoples of the Syr Darya region, around the cities of Turkistan, Sayram, and Sygnak, and later Khorezm, brought significant changes to the cultural life of the Karakalpaks.

Results

During this time, books published in Tashkent, Samarkand, Kabul, and Bukhara began to spread among the Karakalpaks. Among these, alongside epics like "Garib-Ashiq," "Yusuf-Ahmad," "Sayatxon-Hamro," "Hurliqo-Hamro," "Gorogli," and "Yusuf-Zulayxo," books by poets like Navoiy, Mashrab, and Maxtumquli also began to circulate. Due to their small number, copies were also copied and distributed. Some lines have been revised and translated into the Karakalpak language. During this time, Uzbek, Turkmen, and Tajik literature significantly influenced Karakalpak oral literature in terms of language, style, and form, enriching it with new forms [3].

Of course, it cannot be claimed that these epics are being told without distortion, just as they came from their related peoples and Eastern peoples. It is undeniable that these epics have been adapted and reworked over time, adapting them to the Karakalpak people's way of life, national customs, traditions, and way of life. Renowned scholars N. Davqarayev, I. Sagitov, and Q. Maqsetov confirm this in their scientific works. For example, it is known that some of these epics, such as "Garib-Ashiq," "Shasanam," "Sayatxon-Hamro," and

“Gorogli,” were adapted and translated into the Karakalpak language during the 19th century. At the same time, it is known that the bakhshis performed these epics not in their original manuscripts, but by adapting them to the conditions of the Karakalpak people, either adding or borrowing them [6]. The Karakalpak folk bakhshis, who continued the great art of bakhshi and made a great contribution to the transmission of the national heritage of the Karakalpak people - the dastans - to future generations, have made a great contribution. Because epics have been passed down from generation to generation through the path of teacher-student.

The epics performed by folk bakhshis originated in ancient times and trace back to the distinct school of Aral Uzbek bakhshis, which is distinguished mainly by its epic and musical repertoire. The most prominent representatives of this school at the beginning of the 19th century were Sapar Karret the musician, Avaz the bakhshi, Qutim the bakhshi, Janabay the bakhshi, Orimbay the bakhshi, and their students Madreyim the bakhshi, Narbay the bakhshi, Tengel the bakhshi. Their repertoire included folk songs, poems by Maxtumquli, and the epic poems “Yusuf-Ahmad,” “Sayotxon-Hamro,” “Hurlixa-Hamro,” “G'arib-oshiq,” and “Davlatyorbek.” Uzbek bakhshis from Qo'ng'iro't sing with the dutor and have their own unique melodies. Their number exceeds 60. Among them were “Qongirot namasi,” “Bam muhammas,” and variations of “Sarivi,” “Shohi Kishvar,” “Zerletma,” “Remayle,” and “Iraniiy”. The influence of Turkmen bakhshis, especially Suyuv bakhshi, a prominent figure of the 19th century, was particularly significant on Karakalpak and island Uzbek bakhshis. As Q. Ayimbetov correctly pointed out, ‘He was also known as a renowned bakhshi of other peoples who lived in Khorezm’ [5].

The art of Karakalpak bakhshi has developed and flourished thanks to the work of such great masters. Such teacher-student traditions continued. One of them, Japaq Bakhshi Shamuratov, was also mentored by Uzbek bakhshis Amet and Otajon, and Suyev Bakhshi. Suyuv Bakhshi was friends with the renowned Karakalpak bakhshi Musa; they learned the secrets of music from each other and mastered the techniques of epic recitation. Having absorbed the repertoire of such famous bakhshis, having heard, seen, and listened to them, it was Ahmet Tarykhov who dedicated his life to the art of bakhshi. He became a student of Esjon baxshi Qospolatov, a student of Qurboniyoz baxshi, a highly skilled bard, and diligently studied the intricacies of Karakalpak melodies, their performance styles, and the art of epic poetry.

Ahmad Tarixov became a masterful performer of poems based on the lyrics of Maxtumquli, Berdaq, Ajiniyoz, and Kunxo'ja, as well as epic poems like “Qirmandali”, “Garib ashiiq”, “Sayatxon-Xamro”, “Yusuf-Ahmad”, “Bozirgan”, “Gorogli”, and “Qirmandali”.

Ahmet Tariyxov was one of the last bards of the 20th century to pass on Karakalpak bakhshi art to the next generation. During these years, due to the policies of the Soviet Red Empire, the practice of inviting *baxshi* (folk singers) to perform in *qurlar* was abruptly halted, meaning it was not permitted. This continued until the 1970s and 1990s. The people were on the

verge of forgetting this art of storytelling. After our country gained independence, our national traditions, customs, and the art of *baxshi* and *jirov* were revived. Karakalpak folklore is not just the product of a single century, but works that have coexisted and emerged alongside its entire history. These works of art, which have satisfied the needs of the people for a long time and served their interests, are truly folk works. The Karakalpak people have created many artistic oral works throughout their historical journey, passed down orally from generation to generation through the mentorship of teachers and students, and through written books or scribes, conveying them through various methods. The collection, recording, and study of such rich oral folk art of the Karakalpak people has attracted the interest of world scholars. From the mid-18th century until the beginning of the 19th century, Russian scholars became interested in examples of Karakalpak folklore. Muravin and Gladishev, while traveling from Orsk to Khiva in 1740-41, conducted ethnographic notes among the Karakalpaks along the way. P. Richkov also recorded materials related to the Karakalpaks. In 1857-58, the renowned Kazakh scholar Sh. Valixonov visited the Karakalpaks and, having recorded several folklore works, highly praised the Karakalpak art of singing. The artist and writer N. Karazin recorded "The Tale of the Kingdom of Women" from an old woman living in Chimbay and published it in Russian in 1875 in the third volume of the journal "Ancient and New Russia." The Khorezm version of the "Yusuf and Ahmad" epic, widely circulated among the Karakalpaks, was translated into German by the Hungarian Turkologist H. Vambéry in his work “Chigatay Etyuds” and published in 1911 [6]. Examples of Karakalpak folk oral literature were recorded and collected for the first time, and they were published and published in various publications.

Discussion

By the beginning of the 20th century, Russian and local scholars were actively engaged in collecting folklore materials related to the history, culture, social life, and ethnography of the Karakalpak people, particularly recording epics from bards and storytellers. Among the first to do so was the folklorist-ethnographer A. A. Divaev (1858-1935), who, through the head of the Amu Darya department, K. I. Razgonov, recorded the epic poem “Alpomish” from Jiemurat Bekmuhammedov, a Karakalpak bard who lived in the Turtkul volost at that time. A. A. Divaev published it in Tashkent in 1901 in Karakalpak and Russian [7].

In N. Davqarayev's work, he highly praises the work of Russian scholars in collecting Karakalpak oral literature. Karakalpaks pay great attention to the collection of oral folk art, including folk epics. In his work, he writes: A. Rossikova published several Karakalpak fairy tales recorded from various people in Tortkol in Russian in 1901. In 1905, Professor Melioranskiy published a Kyrgyz-Karakalpak version of the song “Edige”. In 1913, A. A. Belyaev visited Turköl, Nukus, Chimboy, and Qo'ng'iro't. He recorded songs like “Edige”, “Qo'blon”, “Shajara”, and a wealth of other folklore materials. Among them, “Edige's Epic”, “Shajara” in the old Arabic alphabet in the Karakalpak

language, and the brief content of “Qoblan” in Russian were published in Ashgabat in 1916-1917 [3].

This was significant for recording and publishing folk epics and oral traditions. This is because the epic provides rich information about the living performance skills of the *jirovs* of that period, their oral language, and the study of folk culture, lifestyle, customs, and traditions.

With the first session of the Writers' Union held in Moscow in 1934, M. Gorky, in his address and speech at the session, stated, “A nation's small or large number does not affect the quality of talent... even small nations have produced many world-renowned works of art... gather and preserve your folklore; the source of artistic expression lies in folklore... Take care of people's talents like Sulaymon Stalskiy” [8] - these words opened up great opportunities in Karakalpakstan for respecting and collecting national heritage. The collection, recording, and publication in the local press of the national written heritage, which was destroyed in 1929-30, began. In particular, recording our national epics from bakhshis and *jirovs* and publishing them has become a pressing issue of the day.

At the initiative of N. Davqarayev, A. Begimov, Q. Ayimbetov, O. Ko'jurov, N. Japaqov, A. Shamuratov, X. Tajimuratov, S. Mavlenov, and Sh. Xo'janiyozov, the collection of folklore samples and the works of pre-revolutionary poets was undertaken.

In the 1930s, together with N. Japaqov and S. Mavlenov, they recorded the epic poem “Qoblon” from Esemurat jirov and published it in 1941. Q. Ayimbetov recorded the epics “Alpomish” from the famous Ogiz jirov in 1934 and “Edige” from Erpolat jirov, and published them for the first time in Moscow in 1937. N. Japaqov published examples of folklore titled “Folk Tales and Songs”. A. Shamuratov recorded the epic poem “Sharyar” from Qulamet Jirov in 1939 and published it in 1940 [6]. 24-25. Furthermore, S. Mavlenov and Sh. Xojaniyozov, who worked extensively on collecting epics and other materials related to folk oral literature, participated in numerous expeditions in the regions of Karakalpakstan and recorded the epics “Qirq-qiz”, “Qurbonbek”, “Shirin Shakar”, “Er Qoshay”, and “Hoji Girey” from Qurbonboy Jirov, the epic “Maspatsha” from Abdimurod Jirov, and “Davlatyorbek” from Qarajon Baxshi [9]. It is known that they also recorded more than 20 folk epics.

One type of Karakalpak folk epic is “*ashqlik*”, or lyrical-epic epics. These epics have long been widely circulated, read, and performed among the Karakalpak people. The “Garib-ashiq” epic has spread among the Karakalpaks in oral and book form, in manuscript copies, and other forms.

In his research “Essays on the History of Karakalpak Literature”, completed in the 1950s, N. Davqaraev, the founder of Karakalpak literary studies, wrote: “Books printed in Tashkent, Samarkand, Kabul, and Bukhara began to spread among the Karakalpaks”.

Among these, alongside epics like “Yusuf-Ahmad”, “Garib-ashiq”, “Sayatxon-Hamro”, “Hurliqo-Hamro”, “Gorogli”, and “Yusuf-Zulayxo”, the works of poets like Navoiy, Fuzuliy, Mashrab, and Maxtumquli also began to spread. These epics spread among the Karakalpaks after the 17th century, especially during

the 19th century, through the Turkmens and Khorezm Uzbeks, either in printed form or in manuscript form. It is noted that Karakalpak bakhshis made their own changes, adapting them to the conditions of the Karakalpak people. He writes, “Most of these epics are recited by bakhshis in the style of the famous Turkmen bakhshi Suyev, who lived for a long time in the 19th century among the Karakalpaks, and the Khorezmian Uzbek bakhshi Eshboy”. Epics have mainly reached us through bards, storytellers, and some attentive people. The Karakalpak people, who have lived together with other peoples since ancient times in the geographical territory where the dastan originated and spread, clearly contribute equally to the creation and formation of the “Garib-ashiq” dastan. Currently, only nine copies of the epic have been recorded. For example: The epic can be considered an improved version, prepared and published by X. Tajimuratov at the Karakalpak State Publishing House in 1960. According to X. Tajimuratov's notes, this version was recorded from the renowned bard Eshon Qospolatov between 1930 and 1934. In addition, a manuscript of Baltaboy the storyteller, who was widely known for his eloquence and style of storytelling, was also used [1]. The manuscript collection of the library of the Karakalpakstan branch of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan holds several versions of the epics “Garib-ashiq”, “Sayatxon-Hamira”, and “Oshiq-Najab”, recorded from Karakalpak storytellers and circulated in manuscript form. For example, copies of the “Garib-ashiq” epic recorded from the renowned Karakalpak storytellers Japaq Shamuratov, Ahmet Tariyxo, and Narbay Koshekenov, as well as copies copied and reworked by Karakalpak scribes in the form of stories from Abutov Habibnazar, K. Medetov, residing in Nukus city, and Baltabaev Yuldash, residing in Qongirot district, are invaluable materials. [9]

Many versions of the epic existed in oral tradition, but unfortunately, it was impossible to collect and record all of them. However, only 9 versions were recorded using all available resources. Three of these versions were published and presented to the public. Currently, only nine copies of the epic have been recorded. For example: The poem was published in 1960 by the Karakalpak State Publishing House. Prepared by H. Tajimuratov and recorded from the famous bakhshi Eshon Qospolatov in 1930-1934. This version, along with the epic poem “Garib-ashiq va Sayatxon-Hamro”, was republished in 1985 and published in Volume XIV of “Karakalpak Folklore” [7]. In the 27-42 volumes of Karakalpak folklore, in the 2011 edition of the Nukus “Ilim” publishing house, N. Kamalov recorded the Amet Tariykhov version of the “Garib-ashiq” epic in 1959 [11, 12].

The subsequent 57-66 volumes, the Qozi Mavlik version of the “Garib-ashiq” epic, were published in the 2013 edition by the Nukus “Ilim” publishing house. Recorded in 1927, transcribed from Arabic script by A. Habibullayev. Currently, these three versions have been published, and the remaining six are held in the manuscript collection of the library of the Karakalpakstan branch of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

There are six versions that haven't been printed yet, and although edited and prepared for publication,

they are still preserved in the manuscript collection. This manuscript was recorded in 1955 by Reyim Qayipnazarov under the title "Garib-Shasanam" and prepared for publication by Sapiura Bavatdinova in 2004. A copy of the version preserved by Zamira, the daughter of Karim jirov Nagimov, was recorded by S. Bahodirova. Prepared for publication by A. Kalenderova with a version by K. Medetov. The Narbay Koshekenov variant was recorded in 1911. The version of Japaq Baxshi Shamuratov, recorded by A. Jamalov, and the version by Xabipnazar Abutov were left unpublished.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the epic poem "Garib-ashiq" has become so widespread among the people that it has not only secured a firm place in the repertoires of every *baxshi* we mentioned above, but its songs have also found a place in the heart of every person. When speaking of love and romance, the people first remember the beautiful lyrical poems from the epic poem "The Stranger in Love".

The epic poem "Garib-ashiq", having traversed such a vast historical path, became a spiritual support and nourishment for our people on its long journey. The people enjoyed it, derived pleasure from it, and drew strength and energy from it. The epic poem "Garib-ashiq" (The Stranger in Love) has reached the contemporary bards of the independence era through the path of such great master bards and their disciples.

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